

High Purity and Special Materials for Electronics

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During the last few decades electronics industry has been recording a phenomenal growth and development and in this process has expanded its need for a variety of ultrapure and special materials for various applications. This technological advancement in electronics industry is synchronised with the availability of the required materials in a state of very high purity. Special materials for specific applications in the electronics industry are the semiconductors, laser materials, luminescent materials, magnetic materials and dielectrics. This article is aimed at a general review of such special materials for the electronics industry.

IN the last few decades the scientific advancement and technological explosion have enhanced the need for a wide variety of synthetic materials. Electronics industry alone has expanded its need for a number of special materials. In addition to the basic materials such as process materials, process chemicals, gases, solvents, surface protection and encapsulation materials, solders, alloys and fluxes which are common with other industries, although required in a higher state of purity, the electronics industry needs special materials for unique applications such as semiconductors, laser and luminescent materials.

Ever since the discovery of transistor a few decades ago there has been a rapid growth and increasing specializations in solid state science. The new materials, by virtue of the utilization of the electronic, magnetic and optical properties of solids in device making, are required to be in a state of very high purity, the impurities being at parts per million to parts per billion level. These materials have further brought into focus physical parameters such as size crystallinity, phases present and crystal quality. The synthesis of such sophisticated materials in ultrahigh purity calls for new techniques such as chemical vapour phase deposition, floating zone melting and suitable environmental conditions. Equally important to the synthesis of these materials is the quality control or the evaluation of the impurities. Modern analytical techniques such as neutron activation analysis, spark source mass spectrometry, emission spectroscopy have been employed for this purpose.

Semiconductor materials

The electrical behaviour in solid state devices depends on careful control of impurities and impurity gradients in semiconductors (Table 1). This calls for ultra-high purity for the raw materials used in semiconductor technology which contain electrically active impurities at parts per billion level and which possess crystallographic perfection. The potential application of a semiconductor is to make use of the electrical and optical effects in solids as in

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND COMPOUND SEMICONDUCTORS

Material	Energy gap (eV)	Band structure	m.p. (°C)	Electron mobility (μ_e) ($M^2/V \cdot sec$)	Hole mobility (μ_h) ($M^2/V \cdot sec$)
Ge	0.72	Indirect	937	0.39	0.190
Si	1.10	-do-	1420	0.14	0.048
InP	1.27	Direct	1070	0.53	0.065
InAs	0.33	-do-	490	3.30	0.028
GaAs	1.38	-do-	1235	0.86	0.025
ZnS	3.60	-do-	1830	0.01	—
CdS	2.40	-do-	1750	0.03	—
GaP	2.24	Indirect			
GaAs _{1-x} P _x	1.44-2.26	Direct-Indirect			

transistors, thermistors, thermoelectric devices, photoelectric cells, solar battery, photo-conductive detectors, phosphors, light emitting diodes and lasers.

Elemental semiconductor

The most widely used semiconductors are the two elements silicon and germanium both of which have diamond cubic structure. They came into prominence with the development of the first germanium transistor in 1946 and the first silicon transistor in 1954. Today, silicon technology has made germanium technology almost obsolete due to the abundance of its raw materials in nature, the high temperature and low leakage characteristics possessed by silicon devices and the impact it has made in the field of microelectronics for the manufacture of integrated circuits.

Compound semiconductors

Elements of group IV, III-V, II-VI of the periodic table can be suitably combined to form compound semi-conductors which generally have the sphalerite or wurtzite structures that are closely related to the diamond cubic structure. Other semiconducting compounds are the group IV-VI and V-VI materials. Gallium arsenide is a

very important compound semiconductor. It finds application either in the pure state or as an alloy in the GaP-As system in varactor diodes, Gunn devices, light emitting diodes, injection lasers, photocathodes, high temperature rectifiers, transistor and solar cells. The current flow in n-type gallium arsenide at field strengths greater than 3 KV/cm gives rise to transverse electron oscillations termed as Gunn effect which is made use of in microwave communication. In this field gallium arsenide has the greatest scope as its conduction electrons have higher mobilities (8000, 3900 and $1600 \text{ cm}^2/\text{VS}$ for GaAs, Ge and Si) and limiting velocities (2×10^7 , 6×10^6 and $9 \times 10^6 \text{ cm/sec}$ for GaAs, Ge and Si) than the other principal semiconductors. Gallium arsenide devices now rely exclusively on epitaxial layers as the active material. This growth of the multilayered structure is generally accomplished either by liquid phase epitaxy or vapour phase epitaxy.

Among the higher energy band gap semiconductors gallium phosphide is of considerable importance. This finds extensive application as LED in the visible region, as dynode material in place of the conventional Cu-Be alloy. Another important application of compound semiconductors is in infrared detectors. Both InSb and InAs are used for this purpose.

Laser materials

Higher power, new wavelengths, tunability, improved ruggedness, reliability, reproducibility, stability and lower prices have combined to bring lasers into daily use. The principle of laser action is 'stimulated emission' in which existing photons stimulate the production of more photons by interacting with excited electrons. Under conditions of thermal equilibrium the lower energy states are more populated than the higher ones and stimulated emission is negligible. A population inversion is therefore an essential condition for laser action.

Lasers are generally classified by the medium in which stimulated emission occurs. Common types of lasers include gas, liquid, solid-state and semiconductor. In each case the physical medium acts as a support for an energy level system the population of which can be inverted by optical pumping, by carrier injection, by electric excitation or by energy released in a chemical reaction.

Solid state lasers (Table 2) are made with both crystalline and amorphous materials, usually in rod form, with excitation accompanied by optical pumping. In these lasers the 'host' comprises the major part of the laser material with the remaining 'active' material (from a fraction of a per cent to 2 per cent by weight) contributing to the lasing action. The most important consideration in selecting compounds for lasers is the size match of the dopant and the host lattice site. Substitution of a similar charged ion in a lattice is more desirable than to have defectors or charge compensators. The laser materials should be optically homogeneous and the crystalline materials must have a high degree of

TABLE 2—SOLID STATE LASER MATERIALS

Host Material	Active ion	Structure	Lasing wave length (μm at 77°K)	Method of preparation
Al_2O_3	Cr^{3+}	Corundum	0.6935	Verneuil
CaF_2	$\text{Nd}^{3+}, \text{Sm}^{3+}, \text{Dy}^{3+}$	Fluorite	1.06, 0.708, 2.36	-do-
LaF_3	$\text{Pr}^{3+}, \text{Nd}^{3+}$	Tysonite	0.598, 1.04	Czochralski
CaWO_4	$\text{Pr}^{3+}, \text{Nd}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$	Scheelite	1.047, 1.065, 2.046	-do-
$\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$	$\text{Nd}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Yb}^{3+}$	Garnet	1.06, 2.09, 1.645, 1.88, 1.03	Verneuil Czochralski

perfection with the impurities distributed uniformly. Most of the lattices so far used have been simple or mixed oxides and fluorides whose structures are related to those of ruby, fluorite, scheelite or garnet. The active ions which cause laser action are that of transition metals, lanthanides or actinides. The width of the emission line will be small if only the above ions are used. The widely used synthetic routes for the laser materials are the several melt-growth methods such as the Verneuil, Bridgman, Czochralski and zone melting techniques and also the technique of growth from solution in high melting fluxes like PbO , PbF_2 , $\text{BaO} + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, NaAlF_6 and alkali earth tungstates. Ruby ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{Cr}^{3+}$) was the first laser to be operated and remains a widely used material particularly for its output in the visible part of the spectrum. The chromium ions (Cr^{3+}) occupy the aluminium sites and are the active centres, their energy levels being determined by the crystal-field splitting of the host lattices. In the case of a three-level system to which ruby belongs, a large pumping power is required for laser action, i.e. for population inversion which can be achieved at lower pumping powers if a four-level system is employed. The rare-earth ions provide energy levels that are needed for operation in the four-level mode. A number of lasers made from rare-earth doped crystals such as CaWO_4 , $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG) and YAlO_3 (YALO) have now been developed. Nd^{3+} doped YAG laser with emission at 1060 nm has been used to produce visible light at 530 nm by the use of a non-linear harmonic generator, namely, $\text{Ba}_2\text{NaNb}_5\text{O}_{15}$. It is easier to achieve optical homogeneity in glasses rather than in crystalline substances. Further, glass as a host offers greater flexibility of size and shape. Nd-glass lasers are currently capable of generating 10^{-11} second pulses, with energies upto 1,000 joules. Limitation to further increases is in the damage threshold of the glass itself. Beam fluxes exceeding 20 to 40 joules per cm^2 will cause deterioration or complete desuruction. Larger diameter rods or further development of face-pumped glass discs could result in productions of higher energies. Until the advent of the transversely excited high pressure gas laser, solid-state lasers were the only type to produce very high peak power in pulsed operation. Peak power is desirable in a number of applications such as plasma/fusion experiments, transmission over long distances, and in systems where nonlinear optical

elements such as frequency converters are used.

The internal efficiency of a GaAs electroluminescent junction is so high that it can be used for laser operation. The laser transitions in semiconductor lasers are associated with the band structure. Actual light emission is obtained at the interface of n and p type bands whenever the electrons and holes are driven into this band junction in a process known as carrier injection. Semiconductor laser materials are predominantly covalently bonded with tetrahedral coordination. A typical homojunction laser is made of a single crystal wafer of GaAs doped with tellurium and zinc to create a p-n junction. The emitted beam is at 904 nm for GaAs. Operation is pulsed, with peak powers upto 100 watts in a single device or 1 KW in an array. Although the emission is stimulated, these are not as directive nor as monochromatic as other laser types. Laser action in ternary compounds was first observed in GaAs_{1-x}P_x crystals and the first laser diodes to operate in the visible region of the spectrum have been made from Ga-As-P alloys prepared by vapour-phase epitaxy. The most recent additions to the semiconductor laser family are the heterostructure injection lasers which operate at room temperatures, are extremely small and are capable of being powered by dry cells.

Luminescent materials

Luminescence is the emission of optical radiation, -uv, visible or infrared, that is the direct result of the energy released during electronic transitions within a material. The luminescence arises from a two-step process in which electrons and holes are generated in concentrations greater than those statistically permitted at thermal equilibrium and a significant fraction of these undergo radiative recombination generating photons. The recombination process is very strongly characteristic of the physical and electrical properties of the material.

Energy can be converted into photons in a variety of ways - thermoluminescence, cathodoluminescence, photoluminescence, chemiluminescence and electroluminescence. The creation of light by fast electron bombardment which is exploited in the communication field, particularly TV, has drawn significant attention towards inorganic luminescent materials since they are most stable to withstand electron bombardment. Typical phosphors (Table 3) include sulphides, silicates, oxides and tungstates. Zinc sulphide is the basic material widely investigated and the best known group among luminescent materials. The commercial development of ZnS phosphors is based on empirical formulae for their preparation. These include the precipitation of the sulphide, the addition of small concentrations of impurity atoms such as Cu, Ag, Au or Mn as activators and the presence of an alkali halide as a flux. ZnS and CdS form a completely miscible system of salts that have sphalerite structure at low temperatures and change to Wurtzite structure above 600°. Light emission may be obtained at any wavelength by appropriate mixing of ZnS and CdS which have

TABLE 3—PHOSPHORS

Compound	Activator ion	Colour characteristics	Area of application
ZnS	Mn	Orange	TV
ZnS	Ag	Blue	
ZnS	Cu	Green	
YPO ₄	Tb	Green	Cathode ray tubes
Y ₂ SiO ₅	Tb	Green	
Y ₃ Al ₅ O ₁₂	Ca	Green	
NaTaO ₄	Tb	Green	
Sr ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ Cl	Eu	Deep blue	TV
YVO ₄ :Y ₂ O ₃ :Y ₂ O ₃ S	Eu	Red	
Gd ₂ O ₃ :Gd ₂ O ₃ S	Dy		
YVO ₄			
La ₂ O ₃ S:Gd ₂ O ₃ S	Tb	X-ray green	X-ray screen Scintillators
CaF ₂	Eu		

luminescence in the blue and infrared region respectively. Tungstate (Mg₂WO₆:W) and phosphate [3Ca₃(PO₄)₂CaF₂:Sb:Mn] phosphors find application in fluorescent lamps.

Considerable amount of research has been directed in recent years towards the development of rare-earth based phosphors and the results show that these new phosphors surpass the conventional ones in several respects. The rare-earth based phosphors employing rare-earths as hosts, activators and sensitizers have found new domains of application, namely, X-ray technology, cathode ray tubes of new capability, fluorescent lamps and infrared emitting diodes. Particular mention should be made about the use of YVO₄:Eu phosphor in colour television and that of the oxysulphide phosphors viz. Gd₂O₃S:Tb and La₂O₃S:Tb in X-ray intensifying screens. As a combination of high luminosity and saturated red hue is desired in colour television, the YVO₄:Eu phosphor, by virtue of possessing these characteristics has gradually replaced the other conventional cathode ray phosphors. The oxysulphide phosphors, by virtue of possessing a high absorption power for X-rays, enable radiologists to get high quality X-ray pictures of patients and also substantially reduce the dosage received by the patients. Y, La, Gd and Lu have 2-6-1-2 outer electron shells; and their 4f shells are either empty (Y and La), full (Lu) or contain the maximum number of unpaired electrons (Gd). Accordingly, they are optically neutral (contribute no colour) and can be used as bases for special purpose glasses. Their oxides are phosphor hosts; since they fluoresce without visible colour.

The biggest step forward in the electronics industry since the transistor is the development of monolithic microcircuitry and in this area electroluminescent devices are playing a prominent role. The combination of semiconduction and luminescence is brought about by depositing phosphors on the surface of a semiconducting glass or glass with a semiconducting film on it, coating the phosphor screens with the conducting and reflecting films of aluminium and applying an electric field across the screen. A wide range of materials—ZnS, ZnSe, CdS,

CdSe, PbSe, PbTe, $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x$, $\text{Al}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{P}$, GaP, GaAs, InP, InAs, BaTiO_3 , SiC, CaWO_4 and ZnSiO_4 have been found to exhibit electroluminescence. Much of the recent interest in the electroluminescent field has been in the area of light emitting diodes (LED).

Electroluminescent devices can be used as radiation sources in place of the tungsten filament lamps. These are rugged, are operated in the cold, can be modulated at high speeds, can be made coherent and can operate at voltages compatible with transistor circuitry. As such, they find application in visual data displays and optical communication systems.

Recent trends in materials research

Considerable amount of activity has been directed in recent years towards the development of photochromic and cathodochromic materials, amorphous semiconductors, liquid crystals and magnetic bubble domain. Photochromic materials have the property of changing colour under light illumination. Photochromic materials under investigation are the rare earth doped CaF_2 and transition metal doped calcium and strontium titanates and they are being tried for application in optical memories for computers and in glasses for achieving variable transmittance. A wide variety of amorphous materials— PbO , CuO , Fe_2O_3 , V_2O_5 , HgO , Cu_2O , Al_2O_3 , Ta_2O_5 , Se, GaP, ZnS, As_2Se_3 —have been found to exhibit transition from a normal high resistance state to a low resistance state in times of the order of microseconds when subjected to a threshold voltage. Memory switches based on this phenomena are under development.

Liquid crystals are organic substances which simultaneously exhibit properties of both liquids and solids over very narrow and specific temperature ranges. There are three types of mesomorphic states—smectic, nematic and cholestric. The last two categories have optical properties which can be made use of in providing a radically new way of converting electrical, thermal and mechanical signals into coloured viewing patterns. Magnetic bubbles, a new way of storing, manipulating and retrieving digital information, offer tremendous potential for improving the logic, memory, counting and switching processes associated with communication systems. They provide information storage at a density of greater than 10^6 bits per square inch and information processing at rates of 1 million bits per second. The central element of a magnetic bubble device requires single crystals of materials with unique magnetic properties that will sustain small bubble like magnetic regions which can move at high velocity. The substituted garnets appear to provide a technological solution to the materials requirement for the bubble domain memory.

Electronic grade purity specifications are absolutely essential since minor amounts of impurities can drastically alter the physical properties of the materials, thereby resulting in undesired device performance. These factors naturally called for

major efforts in developing the process know-how and over the last few years significant advances have been made in this direction.

By and large purification by a single present day method seldom gives the desired purity and, therefore, a combination of methods is sought. For example, in the final purification by zone melting it is imperative that the starting material should already be sufficiently pure, i. e. 99.9% or better, failing which, even under the most favourable experimental conditions either the desired purity is not achieved or the yield of such a product is low. In such cases, as stated earlier, bulk of the impurities can be removed by preliminary chemical or physico-chemical processes prior to zone refining. Equally important for effective removal of impurities is the specificity of the method employed. Both vapour phase and liquid phase epitaxy techniques are employed for the growth of multilayered structure. Gallium arsenide devices now rely exclusively on epitaxial layers as the active material. The reproducible growth of thin layers with the necessary dimensional control is difficult by the above techniques. The advantage, however, is not necessarily dimensional precision, but the high quality of the semiconductor layers. There is another growth technique called molecular beam epitaxy that permits better precision in layer thickness control. The methods normally used for the growth of single crystals are the melt-growth ones such as the Verneuil, Bridgman, Czochralski and zone techniques.

The evaluation of impurities in the processed materials which will determine their (materials) end use requires the development of sophisticated analytical techniques to determine impurities at parts per billion level.

Status of developing special materials for use in electronics industry in India

Until recently the country's requirements of electronic materials have been largely met by imports. The compelling necessity for developing indigenous process and primary materials for electronics industries in the country and, thereby, becoming self-reliant in this field was realised. Accordingly a committee was set-up under the chairmanship of late Dr. H. J. Bhabha which published a report "Electronics in India" in 1966. This report not only emphasised but also quantified the special materials requirement for the electronics industries in the country and also gave a fillip to research and development work on various primary materials in the country. Research and Development programmes were initiated in some laboratories, namely, B.A.R.C., Trombay, N.P.L., Delhi, S.S.P.L., Delhi, N.C.L., Poona, N.A.L., Bangalore and these efforts have started taking definite shape. Based on the process knowhow for various high purity materials developed at Chemistry Division, B.A.R.C., Trombay, a Special Materials Plant has been set up at the Nuclear Fuel Complex, Hyderabad, where a number of high purity materials

which include antimony, arsenic, bismuth, boron tribromide, cadmium, gallium, gold, indium, lead, phosphorous oxychloride, selenium, silver, tin, tellurium, tantalum, zinc etc. are already in production.

The complexities involved in the synthesis, evaluation and utilisation of the sophisticated materials and the rate at which yesterday's innovations are becoming obsolete today in the electronics industry, any materials development programme should be broad-based in line with the growth of electronics in the country in general.

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